

A Comparative Study Of Different Classification Algorithms For The Prediction Of Fake Reviews

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Abstract— In this paper, ML strategy for detecting phoney reviews is proposed. Using a range of feature engineering methodologies, this paper extends beyond the review's feature extraction technique to identify various examiner behaviours. The paper compares and contrasts the outcomes of various programmes. We compared the effectiveness of several classifiers in both cases using an actual dataset of restaurant ratings with and without factors derived from the user's activities. When it comes to the f-score, the remaining classifiers have the highest f-score of 74.79 percent. According to the results. The f-score has grown by 14.14 percent after factoring behavioural characteristics of the reviewers.

Keywords:

Fake reviews, data mining, supervised machine learning, feature engineering.

I. INTRODUCTION

If clients need to make a judgement regarding a service or a product, the primary source of information has shifted to reviews. When customers, for example, take the initiative, they go through reviews on other people's thoughts before taking action. Customers who have used the hotel's services depending on the responses, they determine whether or not to reserve a room based on the reviews. If they do, they most likely received positive feedback from the reviews. Make a reservation for the accommodation. As a result, historical analyses became popular. Most people's most trusted sources of information in numerous areas services available over the internet. Because reviews are regarded as trustworthy sources about favourable and unfavourable services, any effort to influence those rankings by posting misleading evaluations is taken seriously upon. The employment of false information is classified as deceit. The use of false

information is classified as deception. As a result, we're not sure if some of the other written reviews are accurate. What if one or more of these endorsements isn't genuine? Then as conclusion, spotting fake reviews is and will continue to be an essential and crucial field of research.

To a considerable extent, machine learning algorithms can aid in the detection of fake web content evaluations. To detect and extract significant information, web mining approaches employ a range of machine learning algorithms. One of the responsibilities of web mining is content mining. Opinion mining is a classic example of content mining, which involves using machine learning to identify the sentiment of text by training a classifier to examine the attributes of the reviews as well as the sentiments. Fake reviews are typically identified not just by their categorization, but also by certain characteristics that are unrelated to the content. Review features are frequently created using text and (NLP). Fake reviews, but at the other hand, may involve the creation of additional details about the reviewer, such as the time/date of the review or the author's text structures. As a conclusion, recognizing fraudulent reviews requires the development on considerable character recognition from bloggers.

To that end, this paper uses a number of ML classifiers to recognize phoney reviews using the comments' content as well as a number of extracted variables from the reviewers. On a real corpus of reviews, the classifiers are put to the test. This paper uses different features engineering techniques on the corpus to extract distinct reviewer behaviours, in addition to employing natural language processing to extract and feed review characteristics to classifiers. This paper compares the impact of the reviewers' retrieved qualities on the classifiers. The findings correspond in the lack and existence of the retrieved features in two different language models, TF-IDF with bi-grams and TF-IDF with tri-grams. The engineering features, as per the results, boost the performance of the bogus review detecting method.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Since 2007, the challenge of detecting bogus reviews has been addressed. In the Fake review detection investigation, two types of characteristics were used: textual and behavioural features. The verbal aspect of review activity is referred to as textual characteristics. To put things in perspective, the content of the reviews heavily influences the linguistic elements. The nonverbal aspects of the reviews are referred to as behavioural features. They are mainly controlled by the reviewers' behaviours, such as word choice, emotional gestures, and review rate.[1] Although tackling textual features is challenging and important, behavioural features are also important and should not be disregarded since they have a big impact on the false review identification method effectiveness. Several paper studies on fake review identification have heavily used textual features. Around Ten Thousand unfavourable comments about Samsung products and services were gathered in the dataset. The authors used the dataset, which has thousand plus reviews from twenty of Chicago's most popular hotels.[2] To detect fake opinion spamming, the authors utilised neural and discrete models with Average, Convolutional neural network, Recurrent Neural Network, Average, and Bi-directional Average GRNN. They employed a dataset that included both honest and misleading reviews in different like categories. All of the previous studies focused solely on textual characteristics, with no attention paid to behavioural characteristics.

[1] On Amazon reviews, some behavioural variables such as average rating and ratio of the number of reviews written by the reviewer have been taken into account. Another paper looked into the impact of both textual and behavioural elements on the false review detection process, with a focus on the restaurant and hotel industries. In addition, an iterative computing framework plus plus (ICF++) with textual and behavioural elements is proposed. They identified phoney reviews by calculating the honesty value of a review, the trustworthiness value of the reviewers, and the product's reliability value.

To the best of our knowledge, no approaches have delved significantly into extracting features that reflect the reviewers' behaviour, based on the previous explanation. These characteristics will have a significant impact on the success of the bogus review detection approach. [2] This paper presents a machine learning technique for detecting fake reviews. The provided approach, in addition to the review features extraction procedure, uses several features engineering techniques to extract various reviewer behaviours. There are a few new behavioural aspects in this version.

III. BACKGROUND

Several classification algorithms have been developed for supervised machine learning. These algorithms' main purpose is to find a suitable model for spreading training data. SVM is a selective classifier that splits data into categories by finding the best separable hyper-plane that separates the training data. Another common supervised learning algorithm is Naive-Bayes.

$$P(A-B) = P(B-A) * P(A) P(B)$$

NB generates a collection of probabilities by counting the frequency and combined values in a dataset. Character classification, filtering and recommendation are just some number of good areas where NB has proven to be effective.

The KNN algorithm is a straightforward yet powerful categorization technique. The KNN algorithm is commonly used in statistical estimation and pattern recognition. When calculating similarity, the distance function is generally utilised.

[1] In decision tree the algorithm starts by building the tree repeatedly based on the best possible feature split. Specific functions including entropy, information gain, gain ratio, and gini index are used to select the best features. For dealing with overfitting difficulties in decision trees, Random Forest is a viable approach. Random forest's main purpose is to generate a bag of trees from various dataset samples. Random Forest generates a modest random number of features for each tree in the forest instead of producing each tree from all features. Logistic regression is another simple supervised machine learning classifier.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Preprocessing

The first stage in the suggested technique is data preparation, which is among the most crucial steps in machine learning. Because real-world data is never fit for use, image preprocessing is required. To prepare the dataset's raw data for computing activity, this paper used a number of preparation approaches. In a nutshell, it's as follows:

Tokenization: One of the most common natural language processing techniques is tokenization. If we have a text like "sun rise in the east from the beginning of time" tokenization will break it down into the following tokens: "sun" "rise" "in" "the" "east" "from" "the" "beginning" "of" "time".

Stop Words Cleaning: Stop terms are the most commonly used words that have no meaning. Stop words can be found in a variety of contexts (an, a, the, this). Before moving further with the bogus review detection procedure in this paper.

Lemmatization: Lemmatization is a mechanism for converting a plural format to a singular format. Converting the word ("plays") to ("play"), for example.

B. Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is a stage in the pattern recognition or machine learning process that tries to improve performance. Feature extraction is the process of reducing data to its most significant aspects. It is mostly a process for deleting superfluous features from data, which may affect the model's accuracy.

In the literature, several strategies for extracting features for fake review detection have been proposed. [4]It has sentiment categorization, which is based on the percentage of positive and negative terms in the review, such as "strong," "poor," and so on. In addition, the Cosine similarity is taken into account. The TF-IDF approach, which obtains the frequency of both true and false as well as the inverse document, is another textual feature method (IDF) Each term does have its own TF and IDF score, and a term's TF-IDF weight is the total of its TF and IDF scores.

The user's personal profile and behavioural characteristics are the second set of features. These are the two methods for identifying spammers. Whether a user's comment is more frequent and unique than that of other users, or if the person provides a redundant review that has no link to the target site, can be determined using the time-stamp of the user's comment.

C. Feature Engineering

Other descriptive elements of fake reviews are known to include behaviour of reviewers while composing their reviews. Behavioral aspects like as caps-count, punctuation-count, and emojis are taken into account. The total amount of capital characters used by a reviewer when writing the review, the total number of punctuation found in each review, and the total number of emojis in each review are represented by caps-count, punctuation-count, and emojis. We also used statistical analysis on reviewer behaviour by using the "groupby" function, which calculates the number of bogus or actual reviews published by each reviewer on a specific day and for each hotel.

V.EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

On the review dataset, we tested our proposed system. There are 2180 reviews in this dataset . The shortest review is 17 words long, the total size of all reviews is 439.5 words long

Amount of non zero values in the bag of words model: 18277

We retrieved additional features indicating reviewers' behaviour throughout the posting of their reviews in contrast to the dataset and its statistics. Caps-count, which represents the total capital character used by a reviewer while composing their review, and punch-count are two of these features. We'll take all of these factors into account to see how the person's actions affect the models' effectiveness.

We describe the outcomes of various trials, as well as its outcome using five different machine learning classifiers, in this stage. After extracting the features forming the visitor behavior mentioned in earlier part, we use the enlarged dataset. Because the dataset is uneven in terms of true and false labels, we evaluate precision and recall in relation to accuracy, and hence the f1-score is used as a performance index. Seventy percent of the dataset is used for training, with the remaining thirty percent for testing. The classifiers are evaluated initially in the absence of extracted user behaviours and subsequently in the presence of those behaviours.

The validity outcomes in the absence of extracted features behaviours of customers are summarised in Figure II. Each classifier's average accuracy is displayed. The accuracy of decision trees and logistic regression varies. We estimate the total precision of each classifier into account when evaluating the overall results. With 78.23% average accuracy, SVM regression is shown to have the highest average accuracy. Figure 2 presents the conclusions and recommendations.

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Logistic Regression Prediction Accuracy: 77.89%
K Nearest Neighbors Prediction Accuracy: 58.5%
Decision Tree Classifier Prediction Accuracy: 70.24%
Random Forests Classifier Prediction Accuracy: 76.7%
Support Vector Machines Prediction Accuracy: 80.1%
Multinomial Naive Bayes Prediction Accuracy: 74.49%
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Figure. 2.

Each classifiers and their concurrent outputs with their respective accuracy are as follows.

Multinomial Naive Bayes Classification Report:	precision	recall	f1-score	support
CG	0.69	0.90	0.78	296
OR	0.85	0.59	0.70	292
accuracy			0.74	588
macro avg	0.77	0.74	0.74	588
weighted avg	0.77	0.74	0.74	588

Confusion Matrix: [[267 29]
[121 171]]
Accuracy Score: 0.7448979591836735
Model Prediction Accuracy: 74.49%

Logistic Regression Classification Report:	precision	recall	f1-score	support
CG	0.78	0.77	0.78	296
OR	0.77	0.78	0.78	292
accuracy			0.78	588
macro avg	0.78	0.78	0.78	588
weighted avg	0.78	0.78	0.78	588

Confusion Matrix: [[229 67]
[63 229]]
Accuracy Score: 0.7789115646258503
Model Prediction Accuracy: 77.89%

Random Forest Classification Report:	precision	recall	f1-score	support
CG	0.73	0.86	0.79	296
OR	0.83	0.67	0.74	292
accuracy			0.77	588
macro avg	0.78	0.77	0.76	588
weighted avg	0.78	0.77	0.76	588

Confusion Matrix: [[256 40]
[97 195]]
Accuracy Score: 0.7670068027210885
Model Prediction Accuracy: 76.7%

Decision Tree Classification Report:	precision	recall	f1-score	support
CG	0.68	0.78	0.73	296
OR	0.74	0.62	0.68	292
accuracy			0.70	588
macro avg	0.71	0.70	0.70	588
weighted avg	0.71	0.70	0.70	588

Confusion Matrix: [[231 65]
[110 182]]
Accuracy Score: 0.7023809523809523
Model Prediction Accuracy: 70.24%

KNN :- Classification Report:	precision	recall	f1-score	support
CG	0.55	0.96	0.70	296
OR	0.82	0.21	0.33	292
accuracy			0.59	588
macro avg	0.69	0.58	0.52	588
weighted avg	0.69	0.59	0.52	588

Confusion Matrix: [[283 13]
[231 61]]
Accuracy Score: 0.5850340136054422
Model Prediction Accuracy: 58.5%

SVM :- Classification Report:	precision	recall	f1-score	support
CG	0.82	0.77	0.80	296
OR	0.78	0.83	0.81	292
accuracy			0.80	588
macro avg	0.80	0.80	0.80	588
weighted avg	0.80	0.80	0.80	588

Confusion Matrix: [[228 68]
[49 243]]
Accuracy Score: 0.8010204081632653
Model Prediction Accuracy: 80.1%

VI.CONCLUSION

We demonstrated the relevance of reviews in this paper, as well as how they affect practically everything linked to web-based data. Reviews, without a doubt, play an important role in people's decisions. As a result, detecting false reviews is an active and ongoing research topic. A machine learning strategy to detecting bogus reviews is provided in this paper. Both the qualities of the reviews and the behavioural aspects of the reviewers are taken into account in the proposed approach. The dataset will be used to assess the suggested method. In the developed approach, various classifiers are used. The results show that the KNN classifier outperforms the other classifiers in detecting false reviews. In addition, the results reveal that taking into account the reviewers' behavioural characteristics increases the f-score by 14.14%. In the current paper, not all reviewers' behavioural characteristics were taken into account. Other behavioural aspects, such as those based on how often reviewers do reviews, how long they take to complete reviews, and how frequently they post good or negative evaluations, may be considered in future work

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] (PDF) Fake Review Detection From a Product Review Using Modified Method of Iterative Computation Framework (researchgate.net)
- [2] Fake Reviews Detection using Supervised Machine Learning (thesai.org)
- [3] Reviews Detection: A Survey | IEEE Journals & Magazine | IEEE Xplorefake-review-detection/FinalProjectReport.pdf at master · srrivas/fake-review-detection (github.com)
- [4] Fake_Review_Detection/NLP_Final_Project.pdf at master · kushagraagrawal/Fake_Review_Detection (github.com)
- [5] Fake Review Detection | Kaggle(PDF) Fake Review Detection From a Product Review Using Modified Method of Iterative Computation Framework (researchgate.net)